

QUALITY YARN FROM SHORT FIBER

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Abstract

Adding artificial fiber to the short fibers obtained from cotton fiber means obtaining high-quality yarn products and increasing the price of the product in the market economy. It is determined that the strength of the yarn is higher when artificial fiber is added.

Keywords: short fibers, gassing, thread, artificial fiber, viscose fiber, maturity.

Introduction

The properties of natural fibers are unique, and they can be changed a little. Because the basis of these fibers is a molecular compound consisting of cellulose and protein. We can make chemical fibers with different properties. The most valuable advantage of chemical fibers is that they can be quickly and easily changed in accordance with public demand. Various synthetic polymers are used to obtain chemical fibers. When we get yarn from natural fiber, we can get quality yarn by adding physical and chemical substances by changing its properties. In particular, textile products woven from a mixture of chemical and natural fibers achieve their positive properties from products woven from pure fiber. If we add 40-45% lavsan fiber to the composition of natural cotton fiber, we will achieve light, wrinkle-free, firm, friction-resistant and positive properties of the obtained gauze [1-5].

We know that most of the synthetic fibers are extremely soft and fluffy. Therefore, the products made of such fibers do not wrinkle, and they cannot be ironed. It is less soiled, the color of painted items is stable, it is resistant to sunlight and moisture (when washed), weather, moths and does not rot. Chemical fibers can be made waterproof and absorbent in any thickness. We can get quality yarn by synthesizing short fiber or mixing it with chemical fibers [6-14].

Fig. 1. z- turn to the right; s- turn to the left.

Also, the production of chemical fibers does not depend on the unfavorable weather. They can be produced all year round. In addition, chemical fibers are much cheaper than natural fibers. Therefore, if the yarn is made by mixing chemical fibers with natural fibers, the cost of the product will decrease and the quality of the product will increase.

Conclusion

Establishing the production of quality yarn from short fibers coming out of spinning enterprises. In addition to the addition of chemical fibers in obtaining quality yarn from short fiber, it is possible to obtain a quality product and reduce the price in the market.

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